

EQUALITY VERSES QUALITY SYNDROME IN EDUCATION SYSTEM OF INDIA

*Ms. Soumi Mandal,
Assistant Professor,
Dept. of Education, Vinaya Bhavana,
Visva Bharati, West Bengal,
Email.id soumiru@gmail.com, soumi.mandal@visva-bharati.ac.in,
Mobile 8116503122
And
Dr. Sanat Kumar Rath
Assistant Professor
Dept. of Education, Vinaya Bhavana,
Visva Bharati, West Bengal
[Email.id. sanatrath2017@gmail.com](mailto:Email.id.sanatrath2017@gmail.com) , Mob 9800102941*

Abstract

Quality and equity in education are projected as dichotomous in India. It appears that two are different issues of a problem, but there is very little truth in it. They are actually not one against other. In fact they are complimentary to each other. If we look at recent literature, The world Development Report, 2006, titled as 'Equity and development' and the Human Development Report, 2005, both have emphasized on the need for providing equality of opportunity to achieve development. It was also found in Bombay Assembly debate on Bombay University Amendment act in October 1927 that Ambedkar argued for equality of opportunity through representation on the senate for backward class without compromising on the issues of equality. In recent times education should not be an apolitical matter by creating a barrier between the children of oppressed and oppressors through different aspects of pedagogy. The critical pedagogy being proposed here as a tool of consciousness is fundamentally concerned with student's experiences, by taking their problems and needs as their starting point and also suggesting and legitimizing the knowledge through which they will get the meaning to their lives. This paper will raise the issues of quality concerns needed in education system depending on aspects of equality, understanding through different dimensions prevailing in and through the system.

Keywords: Equality, Equity, Quality Education, New liberal policy, Critical Pedagogy.

Introduction

Now-a-days education is in such a state that there is crisis of values and concerns, it is because of prevailing social conditions and lack of political will to change. How is education expected to work within these opposing sets of claim for excellence on one hand and democratic expansion on the other, is a question of concern. The break with the past and the discontinuity which has been affected by colonialism has yet been bridged. It is only now that literatures and perspectives from the period of colonization are being recovered and subaltern histories being reconstructed. The challenges before education are to recover the past without necessarily essentializing it through monolithic interpretations. The need is to decentralize as much as to decolonize, to recognize the multiplicity of our reality and it is also considered that one hegemonic structure is not replaced by another elitist structure which is equally alienating for the pupil. Not only this but this type of educational system also led to the production of culture of silence in the classrooms without addressing the real contexts, indigenous knowledge and native language of a child. So, it is the duty of teachers to treat curriculum as a narrative or voice whose interests must be uncovered and critically interrogated and promote such pedagogical conditions in the classrooms that provide spaces for different student's voices. According to Kumar (1991) the norms of pedagogy that evolved under colonial rule did not weaken with the realization of national independence. Sitting in the classroom today one can still observe the distinct features of teaching that are related to colonial legacy though the small minds are not able to distinguish between the in pedagogic practices of India and West (p 35). In India we are talking about inclusion without recognizing the problems of social exclusion which deliberately categorizes the education system in three different classes of schools; as municipal-panchayat schools for poor, the aided schools for middle class and so-called private-public schools for rich.

Dimensions of equity verses quality

In India we are talking about quality dimensions in almost all the aspects of education starting from continuous teacher's professional preparation to the classroom practices. But quality never be maintained according to differences and diversities of the classroom for addressing their needs. Then what type of quality is actually served in the school system? For example, some Brahmin political leaders argued that an increase in intake of students from backward classes will dilute the standards of higher education by making it elusive. It seems the same kind of arguments continued even after independence raised by Ambedkar. He defined the aim and functions of University education "is to see that the teaching carried on there is suited to adults, that it is scientific, detached and impartial in character, that it aims not so much at filling the mind of the student with facts or theories as at calling forth his own individuality, and stimulating him to mental effort... and gives him a sense of difficulty as well as the value of reaching at truth" (as cited in Chalam, 2008, p 100). It is the ideal situation of higher education which was thought off but presently the higher education system is suffering with a phobia of equity and quality. The real issue here is about the historical conditions under which higher education is developed in the country. It also seems that those who are involved in the policy making failed to consider the inputs of World Bank, UNDP and other thinkers in solving the dichotomy of equity and quality.

From the context of equity and quality we need to understand the concept of 'reservation'. Which become a topic of argument for elitist group of the society like India who don't want equal access and mobility among disadvantaged group. However, according to Krishna Kumar 'reservation is a tool of social transformation should not be happened in one generation' and for Amit Thorat 'reservation is social transformation and building of economic and cultural capital takes time to be passed on from one generation to other'. In support of this a new survey report of SARI 2017 (Social Attitudes Research for India), investigated that most of general

caste and Brahmin people were against reservation by feeling the historically deprived group as their competitors and very few respondents were from SC, ST and OBC who were also against reservation. Because for Hajariprashad Divedi 'in India any lower group or community of people can find another lower community or group of people to ensure their domination on the weaker one'. According to this report some respondents were supporting 'merit' and opposing reservation for equality, yet they did not understand that their argument failed from the distinctions in exam's responses and confident speaking in interviews, is often a result of stressful and unsupportive environment and lack of social and economic support.

All the curriculum frameworks starting from 78, 88, 98, 2000, 2005 or NCFTE 2009-10, were placing different demands and expectations on the teachers by addressing both the initial and continuing teacher education. But how the teachers can make themselves proficient according to the needs of the children it is a point of concern. The teacher's competence, sensitivity and motivation; everything must depend on learner's achievement. Now the question raises that how it is taking place? Whether only through policies which were made properly but not implemented with each passing five year's planning or by addressing learner's demands and their voices in the classrooms. If it is not so then why in one side Right of children to Free and Compulsory education, Act 2009 was made to bring universal elementary education whether in other side the problem of social exclusion is maintained through different types of schools according to different costs paid. Municipal panchayat schools for poor, aided schools for middle class and so-called private-public schools for rich. Not only this rather the input components of elementary education need to discussed which are largely hampered in achieving UEE according to PISA report 2012 (Programme for International Student Assessment). The teacher's backgrounds, beliefs, expectations, motivations, unsatisfactory pedagogical skills, lack of content and context-relevant knowledge and also children's socio, economic and educational backgrounds of families; and linguistic differences in school and home are the most important reasons for

unfulfillment of children's outcome and also achievement of elementary education.

In India education never be an apolitical matter- Michel Apple (1990), Samuel Bowles (1976), Krishna Kumar (1991) and Anil Sadgopal (2004) have argued consistently about the ways in which education is intimately related to the politics in society and, hence is a field of constant struggle between the dominant discourse and those at the margins. Actually it has roots in historical developments because for Kumar (1991) the norms of pedagogy that evolved under colonial rule or colonial legacy did not weaken with the realization of independence.

Among the strategies like NFE (non-formal education scheme), ECG (education for guarantee scheme) or AS (Alternative schooling scheme) are adopted to ensure quality and equity of access to the out-of-school and disadvantaged children must prioritize towards the qualification of teachers, their training, honorarium and academic support. However, the realities of such schemes at ground level are just different because of political interferences leads to inadequate physical infrastructure and appointment of over aged or 40 age of para teachers recruited in *Shishu Shiksha Kendras* in West Bengal (A report of Vimla Ramachandran, DPEP 2001). However, this type of appointments was done intensively on contractual basis to make sure that they do not go to the court for regularization of their jobs as government servants. Not only is this but the school's knowledge reconstructed through several things. We need to understand a scenario of central school where a chapter from history book (ancient India) has been taught; (Ramchandran, 2004)

Teacher: What is Tantricism?

Student 1: Tantricism means belief in magic and superstition.

Teacher: What else you understand from Tantricism?

Student 2: Ma'am it is a mysterious ritual and it's a sign of backwardness.

Teacher: Which areas are mostly affected from?

Student 3: Villages.

Teachers: What type of villages?

Students: (corous answers) Tribal villages.

Neo-liberal impact on education

Now the question that arises is; is the modern education system really providing any consciousness? And what type of knowledge is provided by such schools? It is also recognized from Spencer's famous question about "what knowledge is of most worth?" there lies even more contentious question "whose knowledge is of most worth?" because in low-income countries like India and China, the rate of illiteracy remains high. Overall, among people 15 and older, 29% of males and 46% of females cannot read or write whereas; illiteracy is negligible in high income countries. (World Bank 2000) In India a person is considered as literate who is able to read, calculate and write a simple statement. But this level of literacy is insufficient for the global knowledge economy, in which a secondary level of education is increasingly regarded as basic education. Performance in global economy and functioning in global society requires mastery of technical, interpersonal and methodological skills. Such as, Technical skills include literacy, foreign language, math and science, problem solving and analytical skills; Interpersonal skills include team work, leadership and communicational skills; Methodological skills include the ability to learn one's on, to pursue lifelong learning and to cope up with risk and change; and

Skill of an international language is also one of their basic mottos with a need to ensure that young minds acquire a language with more than just local use, preferably one used internationally. Thus, many of the international schools of Hyderabad, Bangalore and Chennai like metro cities are providing English language including French and Russian as the second languages by eliminating Hindi and Sanskrit languages.

National curriculum is also followed in such schools where everything is a matter of centralized control leaves individual schools unable to react to the local conditions. Its very nature, must involve more bureaucracy than a school-based curriculum, where individual schools must

slavishly implement everything according to the requirement, in a unified manner despite of any bad consequences that may follow from such implementations. So, how it is possible for them for taking into consideration all the life issues of working-class children, who are automatically segregated by several psychological and social-psychological theories of variations in intelligence and verbal-skills tests?

New labour's educational policy modifies and extends Radical Right's Principle and anti-egalitarianism. Business wants education fit for business, so to make schooling and higher education subordinate to the personality, ideological and economical requirements of capital it is making sure that schools must produce compliant, ideologically indoctrinated, pro-capitalist and effective workers. Such policy creates more competitiveness (between schools, parents, students and teachers) and selection (by schools and universities) are a continuation, indeed an extension of more structural aspects of 1988 Conservative Educational Reform Act, in terms of macro structure and organization of schooling. Market have exacerbated existing inequalities by making poor schools, by and large more poor (in terms of relative educational results and total income of the school) and rich or elite schools (in terms of same terms) become richer, which again stimulates the parental choice of elites, choice of curriculum and textbooks, by leaving the neglected class in terms of everything. Thus, we need to analyze such policies and practices, which are also observed through the politics behind textbook writing.

Now the question arises that how to maintain equity and quality despite of such opposing forces?

There are two approaches need to follow, one is the **radical approach** of using pedagogy as a conscious process of the oppressed; and other is **transformative approach** by creating opportunities in the mainstream education for those who are denied access. The very understanding of such issues are more or less imbibed in **critical pedagogy** which viewed us several instances to think critically and develop a general understanding about the hidden reality. Because, the literacy scholars of the New London Group (2000) argues that "the cultural and linguistic diversity

is classroom recourse just as powerfully as it is a social resource in the formation of new civic spaces and new notions of citizenship. This is not just so that educators can provide a better “service” to “minorities”. Rather, such a pedagogical orientation will produce benefits to all. For example, there will be a cognitive benefit to all children in pedagogy of linguistic and cultural pluralism, including for “mainstream” children. When learners juxtapose different languages, discourses, styles and approaches, they gain substantively in meta-cognitive and meta-linguistic abilities and in their ability to reflect critically on complex systems and their interactions” (as cited in Winch, Christopher. & Gingell, 2004).

CONCLUSION

So, it seems very important that all the diversities of a child must be addressed in the classroom by the teachers for creating a counter-hegemonic mobilization against the traditional schooling and neoliberal forces, to help students develop illiteracies necessary for social, political and economic engagement in our new times. It is also true that without entering into the system and understanding the dominant language of the system how a child can survive and develop the skills of deconstructing it. Because for Freire language and power are inextricably intertwined and provide a fundamental dimension of human agency and social transformation (as cited in Giroux, 2005). Language which is shaped by one’s own historical and cultural formation plays an active role in constructing experiences and in organizing and legitimating the social practices available to various groups in society. Also in Gramsci’s terms, language is both hegemonic and counter hegemonic, instrumental in both silencing the voices of oppressed and in legitimizing oppressive social relations (as cited in Giroux, 2005). So, it is the duty of teacher to treat curriculum as a narrative or voice whose interests must be uncovered and critically interrogated and promote such pedagogical conditions in their classrooms that provide spaces for different student’s voices. The **critical pedagogy** being proposed here is fundamentally concerned with student’s experiences, by taking their problems and needs as their starting point and

also suggesting and legitimizing the knowledge through which they will get the meaning to their lives.

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